

Investigations on Kinetics of the Uncatalysed Oxidation of Glycine by Potassium Peroxodisulphate

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Kinetic investigations on this reaction reveal that the singular features of peroxodisulphate involved reactions are largely reproduced. The reaction rate as usual, is first order in peroxodisulphate and independent of the reductant concentration. Prolonged oxidation of glycine is characterised by deamination and degradation of the acid. Arrhenius parameters have been evaluated and the reaction rate is observed to be insensitive to changes in ionic strength. H^+ ions exert a catalysing influence. A tentative mechanism which is quite in conformity with the observations has been suggested.

Uncatalysed oxidations of organic acids by peroxodisulphate ion are being investigated in this laboratory¹⁻⁵. These studies have been undertaken, primarily, to uncover the mechanisms of oxidation in the respective cases, and principally, the important role these postulated mechanisms are expected to play in the $S_2O_8^{2-}$ induced reduction of mercuric chloride by organic acids.

The comprehensive review by House⁶ reveals that only a few kinetic investigations have been made with organic nitrogen compounds and peroxodisulphate⁷⁻¹⁰. There seems no work on record relative to measurements of rates of reaction between amino acids and peroxodisulphate ions. The kinetics of reaction between glycine and $KMnO_4$ has been investigated by Pokrovskaya¹¹, while the Cu-catalysed oxidation of alkaline glycine solutions by periodates has been studied by Kovats¹².

This paper reports the results of the kinetic investigations undertaken to uncover the mechanism of the uncatalysed oxidation of glycine by peroxodisulphate.

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12. Zoltan Kovats, *Magyar Kem Folyóirat.*, 1960, **66**, 181.

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals were of Analar or E. Merck's guaranteed quality. Peroxodisulphate solution was always freshly prepared by direct weighing, before the experiment for reasons of decomposition, although it has been observed that at 60°, the half-life for the thermal decomposition of peroxodisulphate is 49.0 hr—a period so long that the peroxodisulphate concentration could be regarded as constant and its decomposition ignored at room temperature¹³.

The desired volumes of water and standard solutions except for the peroxodisulphate were placed in a glass stoppered flask. The flasks were placed in the thermostat bath having controls within ± 0.1 . Then the proper volume of peroxodisulphate was transferred to the flask by means of a pipette. The peroxodisulphate was not normally preheated to thermostat temperature before addition due to the reason of its decomposition. However, the variation in temperature of the reaction mixture thus caused is insignificant as reported by Allen¹⁴. The reaction kinetics in each run was followed by pipetting out 10 ml aliquots of the reaction mixture and quenching the reaction with ice-cold water. The samples were analysed for residual peroxodisulphate by iodometric titration as described in earlier papers (*loc. cit.*).

RESULTS

The kinetics of the reaction was studied at 50°, employing concentrations of the reactants in stoichiometric proportions (1 : 1 mole). The data of one typical experiment is shown in Table I.

TABLE I

(Glycine)₀ = (K₂S₂O₈)₀ = 0.02M. Temperature = 50°.

Time (mins.)	10	15	30	45	60	90	120	150
10 ³ k (min ⁻¹)	11.65	10.84	10.04	9.92	10.27	10.75	10.91	10.08

A fair constancy of the first order rate constants obtained with equimolecular concentration of the reactants suggests that the overall order of the reaction is one. First order plots were found to be linear for almost the entire reaction and the velocity constants were calculated from the slopes of these lines.

Peroxodisulphate dependence: Fig. 1, is the graphical representation of the 50° rate data of Table I. It can be seen that $t_{\frac{1}{2}}$ remains the same as peroxodisulphate concentration changes from 0.02 M to a value less than 0.01 M in the course of the reaction. This definitely shows that the reaction is first order in peroxodisulphate. Furthermore, the reaction was studied with different initial concentrations of the oxidant. In each case the first order plots in peroxodisulphate concentration were found to be linear. Table II summarises the results obtained.

13. W. K. Wilmarth and Co-workers, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, **63**, 353.

14. T. L. Allen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **87**, 3589.

At higher concentrations of peroxodisulphate, the reaction rate appears to decrease. This decrease may be attributed either to the increase in the ionic strength (due to higher $S_2O_8^{2-}$ concentrations) or to the specific inhibiting action of K^+ ions, since K^+ ions are known to inhibit $S_2O_8^{2-}$ oxidation¹⁵. As will be seen later, the reaction rate is insensitive to changes in ionic strength and it seems probable therefore, that K^+ ions exert an inhibitive effect.

TABLE II

Conditions same as in Table I

Initial conc. of oxidant (M) :	0.02	0.03	0.04
$10^3 k$ (min ⁻¹) :	10.6	9.67	8.29

Glycine dependence : The reaction was likewise studied with different initial concentrations of glycine, keeping peroxodisulphate constant. The results are recorded in the following table.

TABLE III

Conditions same as in Table I

Initial conc. of glycine (M) :	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.05
$10^3 k$ (min ⁻¹) :	10.9	10.6	11.0	12.1

The values of the rate constants cited above show that there is no significant effect of glycine concentration on the reaction rate. This suggests the rate law to be zero order in the reductant concentration. The order of this reaction with respect to glycine, on calculating by Isolation method, comes out to be 0.08. It is therefore, concluded that the order of the reaction with respect to glycine is zero.

 15. (i) S. P. Srivastava and S. Ghosh, *Z. Phys. Chemie*, 1957, **207**, 161.

 (ii) Y. K. Gupta and S. Ghosh, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, **11**, 62.

 (iii) D. D. Mishra and S. Ghosh, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 402.

Temperature dependence: The effect of temperature on k over a range of 40–55° is given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

$$(\text{Glycine})_0 = (\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_0 = 0.02 \text{ M}$$

Temperature (°C)	40	45	50	55
$10^3 k$ (min ⁻¹)	2.91	5.79	10.6	20.2

The Arrhenius plot of this data is linear (fig. 2) and gives

$$k = 3.63 \times 10^{15} \exp(-25,780/RT) \text{ min}^{-1}$$

Effect of neutral salts: The effect of different neutral salts was studied. The following table summarises the average values of the rate constants in presence of different electrolytes.

TABLE V

Conditions same as in Table I

	Concentration of added electrolyte (M)	Ionic strength	$10^3 k$ (min ⁻¹)
	—	—	10.60
K_2SO_4	0.0125	0.0375	1.68
K_2SO_4	0.020	0.0600	1.64
K_2SO_4	0.025	0.075	1.57
KCl	0.050	0.050	1.81
CH_3COONa	0.050	0.050	2.42

Apparently the rate constants are observed to decrease with increasing ionic strength. But a close scrutiny reveals that the decrease in the rate constant is not strictly related to increase in the ionic strength, as is evident on comparing the rate constants and the ionic strengths contributed by different concentrations of potassium sulphate. Moreover, in the case of KCl and sodium acetate, where though the ionic strengths are equal, the rate constants are observed to differ widely. Evidently there is considerable specific effect of the ions (like cation K^+) and the increase in the ionic strength does not appreciably influence the reaction rate. Similar observations have been obtained by Ghosh *et al.*¹⁶, Levitt and Malinowski and Bartlet and Cotmann¹⁷.

The results suggest that the rate determining process could involve a neutral molecule and an ion.

Effect of H^+ ions : To find out the effect of H^+ ions the reaction was studied in the presence of H_2SO_4 and HCl in two different runs. The values of the rate constants obtained showed the rate to be enhanced in presence of H^+ ions.

Effect of mercuric chloride : Peroxodisulphate—glycine system did not reduce mercuric chloride to the mercurous state as was observed in other systems. It can therefore, be concluded that the free radical responsible for the reduction of Hg^{2+} ion is not produced in this system.

DISCUSSION

For the interpretation of the kinetic data recorded herein, the chain initiation is ascribed to the thermal decomposition of peroxodisulphate ion which undergoes fission of the weak O—O bond with the production of two sulphate radical ions (*loc. cit.*), as shown below :

In a recent review, Wilmarth¹⁸ maintains these free radical ions to be energetically capable of initiating the oxidation process by reacting with the organic substrate and with the solvent, though with unequal efficiencies. Reaction with the latter involves the slow but relatively faster than (I), seq.:

The oxidation of glycine would then occur through the following rapid sequence :

The hydroxyl free radicals in turn rapidly decompose the oxidising ions present by the following sequence :

16. D. D. Mishra and S. Ghosh, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 397.

17. S. Ghosh *et al.*, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, **11**, 62, 320.

(ii) Levitt and Malinowski, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 4517.

(iii) Bartlet and Cotmann, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 1419.

18. W. K. Wilmarth and A. Haim. "Peroxide reaction mechanisms conference" Providence, Rhode Islands, 1960, p. 175.

The above reaction scheme gives the rate of disappearance of peroxodisulphate as :

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{d\text{CS}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}}{dt} &= k_1 \text{CS}_2\text{O}_8^{2-} + k_4 \text{C}_{\text{OH}} \cdot \text{CS}_2\text{O}_8^{2-} \\ &= (k_1 + k_4 \text{C}_{\text{OH}}) \text{CS}_2\text{O}_8^{2-} \\ &= k_{\text{obs}} \text{CS}_2\text{O}_8^{2-} \end{aligned}$$

where $k_{\text{obs}} = (k_1 + k_4 \text{C}_{\text{OH}})$

which is a satisfactory representation of the kinetic law, for it explains the observed first order kinetics in peroxodisulphate and the increase in rate of disappearance of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ in presence of the additive (glycine). Our experimental data of Tables (I-III) show the rate to be first order in $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and independent of the reductant concentration.

Reaction-sequence (II) also finds support from observed insensitivity of the rate to changes in ionic strength (Table V). Furthermore, the suggested mechanism steps do not involve the production of CO_2^- radical. The glycine- $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ system should therefore, not reduce HgCl_2 ¹⁹ and our experiments (with added HgCl_2) revealed such to be the case.

H^+ ions have been found to catalyse the aqueous decomposition of peroxodisulphate²⁰. This results in enhancing the reaction rate in presence of acids and its decrease in presence of sodium acetate.

Deamination is characteristic of amino acids and Kovats (*loc. cit.*) has oxidatively deaminated glycine in presence of KOH and Cu; the oxidant being KIO_4 which is found to behave like H_2O_2 under the circumstances. Pokrovskaya shows NH_3 and HCN to be the probable products of oxidation of glycine with KMnO_4 . However, the nature of oxidant employed also affects the resulting products. Peroxodisulphate is a less potent oxidant than KMnO_4 under comparable conditions and our stoichiometric investigations approximate as :

(Found : 1 mole $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$: 1 mole glycine)

Observed evaluation of CO_2 is indicative of the degradation of glycine. Identification of formaldehyde was marred, probably because of its reaction with NH_3 and its further oxidation to formic acid also seems untenable since the system is not found to reduce HgCl_2 . Furthermore, the uncatalysed oxidation of formaldehyde by peroxodisulphate has been reported to be very slow, about one tenth of the reaction taking place in six to 8 hr.²¹ It may therefore be concluded that oxidation of glycine occurs mainly as shown by equation (III) i.e.,

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19. K. Kumar and L. K. Saxena, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 669.
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21. K. C. Khulbe and S. P. Srivastava, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1962, **60**.